

Sparse, Random Array Processing for Space-Based Radar

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Abstract – We investigate moving target detection with a space-based cluster of radar satellites, modeled as a random sparse array. Results show that improvement in signal to interference is a sensitive function of the pulse repetition frequency and varies over a large dynamic range. Achievable improvement factor maxima are moderately degraded by array pitch (satellite cluster rotation) and strongly degraded with increasing position errors. In general, with increased randomness, fewer elements contribute to form DPCA pairs so that satellite usage efficiency and SNR are degraded.

I. INTRODUCTION

We describe the use of large, spatially thinned arrays for the space-based radar detection of slowly moving ground targets. Sensitive detection from the rapidly moving, space-based platform depends on observing small differences in the Doppler frequency of the signal scattered from the moving target and ground clutter or clutter. The nearly monochromatic Doppler frequency of the slowly moving vehicle must be outside the Doppler frequency bandwidth of the power spectral density of the ground clutter, controlled principally by the two-way antenna power pattern of the radar. Improved detection requires reducing the power spectral density within the bandwidth of the slowly moving vehicle as determined by vehicle acceleration, scatter fluctuations and the coherent dwell time of the radar. Within this conventional view, reducing the power spectral density of the ground clutter in this Doppler frequency band can be achieved by (1) narrowing the beamwidth of the two way antenna pattern and thus, the bandwidth of the ground clutter, (2) introducing nulls into the receive antenna pattern at Doppler frequencies of ground clutter corresponding to the vehicle Doppler frequencies, and (3) using narrowband filters with bandpass properties that complement those of the receive antenna. However, these techniques degrade timely wide area surveillance since they require large, narrow beamwidth antennas with many azimuth resolution cells within the surveillance sector, and long coherent integration times. In addition, the use of large antennas with well-controlled sidelobes is likely to be costly. Alternatively, displaced phase center array (DPCA) and other more general space-time techniques offer sensitive slow speed target detection, but require substantial antenna pattern control, processing, and restrictions on the

radar pulse repetition frequency (PRF) that may not be suitable for sparse, random arrays.

The US Air Force TechSat21 [1] is a multi-function space-based sensor concept that employs a cluster of identical, free-floating, semi-autonomous and self-organizing satellites to form a large space aperture. Contemplated missions include surveillance radar detection and location of moving vehicles, synthetic aperture mapping, emitter location, and both local area and wide area communications. The use of small, free-floating satellites has the potential for the accomplishing the multiple missions of the sensor at reduced cost, while allowing for gradual performance enhancement and sensor maintenance using residual space launch capabilities over time. Perhaps the most demanding mission for this sensor is the wide area detection of slowly moving vehicles, considered here. We envision each satellite transmitting its own, possibly orthogonal signal and receiving the reflected signals from all satellites, similar to the French RIAS ground based system [2]. The satellites are envisioned to operate coherently at X-band (3 cm wavelength). Thus, the cluster forms a large, sparse, multi-element, time varying phased array with narrow beamwidth and concomitant grating or random sidelobes that introduce significant ground clutter into the received signal. Previous work described approaches to distributed space-based radar employing satellites in a single orbital plane [3,4,5,6,7,8]. In our previous work [9,10,11,12,13], the satellites were assumed to be in multiple, nearly circular, low Earth orbits with a common orbital plane and thus form a sparse, periodic, two dimensional transmit-receive array with limited along track dimension operating at one of a carefully selected set of PRFs. The PRFs are selected to exploit the nearly periodic array pattern structure maintained throughout the Earth orbit to achieve nearly optimum, displaced phase center cancellation of ground clutter. The performance of the optimum receive signal space-time processing for the detection of slowly moving ground targets was presented and compared with simpler, but sub-optimum, separable or sequential array-pulse processing architectures.

Even though Kepler's laws of orbital mechanics tend to preserve the periodic array structure found necessary for optimum ground clutter suppression, second order effects such as differential satellite drag and gravitational perturbations, as well as limited deployment precision, may make it difficult to create and preserve the necessary array periodicity with limited satellite fuel consumption. Therefore, in this paper we

compare the detection performance of an array composed of satellites randomly distributed within the same limited aperture to determine the loss of performance due to fuel limitations. The satellites are assumed to perform autonomous station-keeping with knowledge of the other satellite positions and velocities only to maintain position within the aperture boundaries and avoid collisions. It is assumed that global knowledge of the satellite positions and velocities is available and used for waveform and satellite scheduling and coherent transmit-receive signal processing.

In this paper we discuss the performance of linear and planar arrays of satellites randomly located in a confined region of a single orbital plane. In the most general design case, we may choose the satellite locations, transmit waveforms and receive space-time processing to maximize the ratio of target signal power to clutter and noise interference. In the current scenario, however, the random but known satellite positions restrict design parameters to include only the transmit waveforms and receive signal processing. The sparse, random linear array to be discussed initially serves as a primitive model for the leader-follower configuration of satellites in a single, circular orbit. In addition, the linear array is easily analyzed and provides insight into the conditions for optimum space-time signal processing as well as necessary conditions on the transmit waveforms. These insights are useful for interpreting the space-time processing for the random, planar array, where Earth rotation and intra-array satellite motion complicate the design for maximum signal to interference.

II. LINEAR ARRAY PERFORMANCE

In this section, we consider an array of N radiating elements randomly positioned along a line within a specified aperture determined by the radar search rate and minimum target speed for detection. The random element positions are assumed known from measurement and the element orientations are such that the elements have common radiation patterns. All elements move parallel to the aperture with identical, constant speeds. The array transmits P pulses broadside to the array. Two cases are of interest. In one case, the array transmits coherently with a maximum gain, uniform illumination at each pulse. In the other, each element transmits with its own orthogonal waveform and associated receive matched filtering allows isolation of each transmit element/receive element channel. The time between pulses is not necessarily fixed, allowing for either fixed or staggered PRF during a specified illumination period determined by the radar search rate.

Using the random but known array element positions, we select the receive array space-time processing and details of the transmit waveform to maximize

$$\frac{\mathbf{w}^H \mathbf{S} \mathbf{w}}{\mathbf{w}^H (\mathbf{C} + \mathbf{N}) \mathbf{w}}, \quad (1)$$

the Rayleigh quotient of the receive signal power to interference (clutter plus receiver noise) power as a result of the ar-

ray space-time signal processing. In this expression, \mathbf{w} represents a column vector of space-time processing weights to be determined (\mathbf{w}^H is the conjugate transpose of the vector), and \mathbf{S} , \mathbf{C} and \mathbf{N} represent target signal, clutter and receiver and interference noise covariance matrices, respectively, for the space-time receive array samples. In this portion of the study, the target signal covariance matrix is found assuming that the target is broadside to the array with a radial ground speed that has a Gaussian distribution with zero mean and parametric standard deviation. The clutter is assumed uniformly distributed and uncorrelated in angle and exhibits no internal motion or intrinsic Doppler spread. The receive signal processing weights that maximize the Rayleigh quotient of signal to interference are easily determined in terms of the signal, clutter and noise covariance matrices [14].

However, the signal to interference ratio depends implicitly on the transmit waveform and transmit array pattern via the signal and clutter covariance matrices, \mathbf{S} and \mathbf{C} . The optimization process with respect to these design parameters is not apparent. Instead, we pursue a study of the signal to interference ratio with optimum space-time weights as a function of the transmit waveform for fixed maximum gain transmit arrays to determine necessary conditions for the transmit waveform. We have shown [13] that a generalized DPCA condition [15] must be satisfied by the random array structure and transmit waveforms.

We summarize the properties of the receive signal space-time covariance or correlation functions. The space-time samples must be highly correlated to achieve coherent receive signal processing. An analysis similar to that given by Ward [16] indicates that for a common transmit array moving along the array axis, the correlation between the signal received at element a with position d_a at time t_1 and the signal received at element b with position d_b at time t_2 is a function of the space-time difference variable

$$\xi = \frac{2V_R(t_1 - t_2) + (d_a - d_b)}{\lambda}, \quad (2)$$

where V_R is the radar array speed along the array and λ is the radar wavelength. No pitch or yaw motion of the array is included here and all receive elements are assumed to move with the common along track speed. The space-time signal correlation function for a periodically thinned array is periodic in ξ with a period that is the array inter-element spacing [13]. The envelope of the correlation function decreases linearly, corresponding to the decreasing number of simultaneous, overlapping elements contributing at a given space-time separation. The details of the correlation function at each peak depend principally on the array or satellite element aperture distribution.

The space-time correlation function for received signals in the randomly thinned array has peaks that occur at the $\binom{N}{2}$ non-zero inter-element spacings, where N = the number of elements and $\binom{N}{2}$ is the binomial coefficient representing the

number of combinations of N elements taken two at a time [13]. Peaks are at a relative correlation level of $1/N$ when compared to the correlation of 1 when $\xi=0$ and again the correlation function at each peak depends principally on the array or satellite element aperture distribution.

These observations lead to the conclusion that for the periodic array, inter-pulse receive samples should be such that the space-time difference variable should be $\xi=0$ or a small multiple of the common inter-element spacing of the array to insure coherence between the receive samples and enable coherent receive signal processing. On the other hand, for the random linear array, we must require that $\xi=0$ or, if there happen to be a large number of common inter-element spacings, we may let $\xi =$ those spacings. The condition that $\xi=0$ leads to a generalized DPCA condition on the positions and times at which space-time samples are acquired for coherent processing,

$$V_T t_1 + d_a + V_{Ra} t_1 = V_T t_2 + d_b + V_{Rb} t_2, \quad (3)$$

where in this expression V_T is the along array speed of the transmit source, and V_{Ra} and V_{Rb} are the along array speeds of the receive elements, a and b, respectively. We assume that the time delay to the target and clutter, τ_d , is such that

$$\delta V_R \tau_d / \lambda = |V_{Ra} - V_{Rb}| \tau_d / \lambda \ll 1, \quad (4)$$

which is a measure of the uniformity of receive element speed required for clutter cancellation. Condition (3) represents a conservation principle directing the choice of space-time samples for coherent processing. The principle indicates that the sum of the distances from a reference point in the array to the transmit phase center and the appropriate receive element must be conserved between space-time samples.

Physically, this conservation principle assures that the path length delay (phase shift) of all signals from stationary scatterers in the far field of the array is the same at the two observation times, independent of the scatterer aspect angle with respect to the array [13]. Thus, subtraction of the space-time samples should cancel the reflections from stationary scatterers at all aspects with respect to the array. However, a moving scatterer such as a moving target or ground reflections with internal motion (e.g. trees moving in the wind) will not be cancelled. Indeed, for sensitive detection of a slowly moving target, there should be a π phase change between time samples at the minimum radial speed of the target, for in this case, the received time samples will add.

The conservation principle dictates the distribution of inter-pulse times ($t_2 - t_1$ in (3)) for each random array realization necessary for coherent processing. Figure 1 illustrates one such distribution. Here we show the complementary cumulative distribution (fraction of samples exceeding the abscissa value) of inter-pulse times, normalized to the array transit time (the time for the array to travel one array length). This distribution is for 20 elements uniformly distributed across a 1000 wavelength aperture. Distributions are selected such that there is a 20 wavelength zone around each element from which other elements are excluded for safety purposes. The small plateau in the distribution function near zero is due to

Fig. 1. Complementary cumulative distribution function for normalized inter-pulse times for a linear array of 1000 wavelengths with 20 elements and a 20 wavelength exclusion zone around each element. The normalized inter-pulse time is the time between receive samples divided by the time for the array to move one array length.

the presence of this exclusion zone.

Notice that the largest portion of the inter-pulse times is near zero. For example, in this realization, only 28% of the normalized inter-pulse times exceed 0.25. However, for sensitive moving target detection, we require a significant number of inter-pulse times that are large to insure that there is a significant phase change between samples for the slowest radial speed target to be detected. A significant number of pulse pairs greater than that required for minimum speed target detection are required to achieve sufficient signal to noise for detection. These considerations determine the size of the sparse array. For example, to detect a target at 2.2 m/s (5 mph) from a satellite formation in low Earth orbit (850 km) at an orbital speed of 7.5 km/s would require an aperture of about $3.3 \cdot 10^3$ wavelengths (approximately 100 m at X band). Here we have assumed that the normalized inter-pulse time is 0.25.

The fact that with the random, sparse array only a subset of all array receive elements satisfy the generalized DPCA condition and participate in the clutter cancellation causes degraded target signal to noise when compared to the periodic array of the same size. This is illustrated in Figure 2. Here the *improvement factor* (IF) is the signal to interference after sparse receive array beamforming and signal processing normalized to the signal to interference at the output from a single receive element with a fully filled, maximum gain transmit array of the same aperture size. The abscissa represents the relative RMS target speed, expressed as the standard deviation of the target Doppler frequency when the target speed/frequency is Gaussian distributed with zero mean, normalized to the -3 dB, two-way, half beamwidth of the thinned array antennas. The improvement factor is given by the solid curves for 2, 3 and 4 pulses processed (increasing values of the improvement factor respectively) at a constant PRF corresponding to the DPCA condition for one inter-element spacing of the random array. For comparison, the improvement factor for a corresponding periodically thinned array with 2, 3 and 4 pulses is shown by the dashed curves.

The asymptotic values of the improvement factor for large RMS target speeds are limited by the receiver noise assumed in the calculations.

The randomly thinned array fails to achieve an improvement in signal to interference that is comparable to the periodically thinned array since the random array has fewer space-time receive samples that satisfy the DPCA condition for a given PRF than does the periodic array. This is confirmed by observing the optimum receive aperture weights for two successive received pulses in the periodic and random arrays. For the random realization illustrated here, only three elements in the array satisfy the DPCA condition while for the periodic array, 18 of the 20 elements satisfy the condition. Thus, the residual signal to noise at large relative RMS target speed is reduced by $3/18 = .17$ (-8dB) as occurs in Figure 2 for two pulses.

III. PLANAR, RANDOM ARRAY PERFORMANCE

In earlier papers [9-12] we analyzed a planar periodic array in one orbital plane with carefully chosen PRFs and demonstrated this to be an ideal case for optimum clutter suppression. However, controlling the satellites to maintain the exact positions of a periodic grid may not be possible. Therefore we now analyze how performance degrades, first with array pitch and yaw and second, with random but known element position errors. We do this as a function of PRF, since this is our principal design variable.

A. The Array Model

Our approach is based on a vertical planar array of 19 small ($2 \times 2 \text{m}^2$) X-band phased array satellites. The vertical orientation in a single orbital plane allows looking toward both sides equally well with simple satellite maneuvers and gives the highest gain at the maximum range. The array configuration

has one central element and six elements on each of three concentric 2:1 ellipses to provide a periodic triangular grid. During one Earth orbit, the elements will rotate one full cycle along their respective ellipses but maintain a triangular grid. General space-time processing and uniformly distributed target ground speeds are assumed.

Representative results will be shown for nominal satellite altitudes of 850 km, an orbital plane inclined 70° relative to the equator, satellite positions 45° above the equator, and look angle 45° down. In this analysis, 'pitch' implies that the satellite velocity vector differs from the array axis direction but lies in the orbital plane of the array. It is caused by the array rotation during orbit. 'Yaw' implies a velocity component orthogonal to the plane of the array and is caused by Earth rotation.

For reference, Figure 3 shows the improvement factor (IF) vs. PRF for 0° pitch and yaw for the periodic array. This is the optimal case. There are several PRFs which give large improvement in signal to interference and satisfy the generalized DPCA condition. However, these large improvements are extremely narrow band indicating the requirement for precision selection of PRF and precision measurement of satellite positions and orientations. At a pitch angle of 5° deg., which represents one of the more difficult cases during an orbit translation, there are many more IF maxima and the minima are less deep [13]. This is due to the fact that the rotated array presents a larger set of inter-element spacings and thus a larger set of DPCA pairs

B. Effects of Random Position Errors

We investigate array performance degradation when the satellite cluster cannot be controlled to maintain a perfectly periodic grid. To model this situation we distribute the array

Fig. 2. Improvement in signal to interference as a function of relative RMS target speed for periodically and randomly thinned arrays.

Fig. 3. Improvement factor vs. PRF for the 19-element array with 0° pitch and yaw.

elements randomly within square boxes, which are centered at the periodic grid points and contained in the single orbital plane of the array. Assuming the position errors known, we again compute the improvement factor as a function of pulse repetition frequency for various error box sizes.

Figure 4 shows the improvement factor vs. pulse repetition frequency for our 19 element array with 0° pitch and yaw for error boxes 1m and 5m on the side, for one random but known realization. The case with no position errors in Figure 3 serves as a reference. With increasing position errors, the number of significant IF maxima increases while their peak values decrease. This is again because there is a richer set of element spacings, but, at any one frequency, fewer elements contribute to form DPCA pairs.

IV. ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

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Fig. 4. Improvement factor vs. PRF for random position errors within 1m and 5m boxes (0° pitch and yaw)